

Yashil IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
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Bosh muharrir:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

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Muharrir:

Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

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RELEVANCE OF BENCHMARKING IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES

Uktamjonova Zulayxo Anvarjon qizi

Assistant, Department of Management, Fergana Polytechnic Institute,
Fergana, Uzbekistan

Abstract: In the conditions of the market economy, in the conditions of constant global competition, constant improvement of industrial enterprises, optimization of competitive characteristics and production, creation of all internal opportunities, and preservation of competitive advantages are urgent tasks. The ambiguous side of this problem is that the emergence of new directions, methods and appropriate means of achieving and forming competitiveness led to the preservation of the enterprise's advantage. One of the most effective tools that allows enterprises to constantly increase profitability, improve the quality of its results, and stay ahead of competitors is the use of benchmarking technology.

This article shows how to develop a competitive strategy for our national enterprises by comparing the experiences of foreign enterprises.

Key words: opportunities, constant global competition, benchmarking, enterprise advantage, business process analysis.

Annotatsiya: Bozor iqtisodiyoti sharoiti va doimiy jahon raqobati sharoitida sanoat korxonalarini doimiy ravishda takomillashtirish, raqobatbardoshlik xususiyatlari va ishlab chiqarishni optimallashtirish, barcha ichki imkoniyatlarni yaratish, raqobatdosh ustunliklarni saqlab qolish dolzarb vazifalardir. Ushbu muammoning noaniq tomoni shundaki, raqobatbardoshlikka erishish va shakllantirishning yangi yo'nalishlari, usullari va tegishli vositalarining paydo bo'lishi korxonaning ustunligini saqlab qolishga olib keldi. Korxonalarga doimiy ravishda rentabellikni oshirish, uning natijalari sifatini yaxshilash va raqobatchilardan oldinga ilgarilash imkonini beradigan eng samarali vositalardan biri bu benchmarking texnologiyasidan foydalanishdir.

Ushbu maqolada xorijiy korxonalar tajribasini solishtirish orqali milliy korxonalarimiz uchun raqobat strategiyasini ishlab chiqish ko'rsatilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: imkoniyatlar, doimiy global raqobat, benchmarking, korxonaning ustunligi, biznes jarayonlarini tahlil qilish.

Аннотация: В условиях рыночной экономики, в условиях постоянной глобальной конкуренции, постоянное совершенствование промышленных предприятий, оптимизация конкурентных характеристик и производства, создание всех внутренних возможностей, сохранение конкурентных преимуществ являются актуальными задачами. Неоднозначная сторона этой проблемы состоит в том, что появление новых направлений, методов и соответствующих средств достижения и формирования конкурентоспособности привело к сохранению преимущества предприятия. Одним из наиболее эффективных инструментов, позволяющих предприятиям постоянно увеличивать прибыльность, улучшать качество своих результатов и опережать конкурентов, является использование технологии бенчмаркинга.

В данной статье показано, как разработать конкурентную стратегию для наших национальных предприятий путем сравнения опыта зарубежных предприятий.

Ключевые слова: возможности, постоянная глобальная конкуренция, бенчмаркинг, преимущество предприятия, анализ бизнес-процессов.

INTRODUCTION

Today's market economy, unstable external environment, constant global competition, constant improvement, competitiveness and optimization of production, creation of all internal capabilities, and ability to maintain competitive advantages are urgent tasks of industrial enterprises. The ambiguous side of this problem is that the emergence of new methods, techniques and related tools to achieve and form competitiveness led to the preservation of the advantage of the enterprise. One of the most effective tools that allows the company to constantly increase productivity, improve the quality of its results, surpass competitors, use comparison technology, comparison is used as an aid to stabilize production in a situation where the enterprise may not work

efficiently structure. The way to do this is to focus on the best results and experiences of other businesses. Unfortunately, benchmarking in industrial enterprises in Uzbekistan is very limited¹. Therefore, the problem of introducing the main elements of benchmarking in the activity of industrial enterprises and determining its impact on the effectiveness of marketing activities, using foreign experience is very relevant today.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The work of foreign authors specially devoted to benchmarking: R. Kamp, B. Andersen, S. Miller, F. Kotler, D. Traut, the theoretical basis of the research is provided by local experts: E.A. Mikhailova, G.L. Bagieva, G.L. Azoeva, A.P. Chelenkova, I.A. Arenkova, A.K. Kazantseva, E.P. Golubkov's² views are reviewed in this article.

In addition, the importance of developing industrial enterprises, especially textile industry clusters, was emphasized by S.S. Gulomov, N. Kh. Jumayev, M. Sharifkhojayev, Yo. Abdullayev, economists of our republic N.Q. about some theoretical and practical aspects of improving management processes in cluster enterprises Oh. 'Idoshev, M.R. Boltabayev, Z.T. Ghaibnazarova, E.A. Mominova, Z.A. Hakimov, S.Sh. Yusupov, I.A. The scientific researches of Toshpolatov, N.A. Yoldasheva are studied in this article.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Comparative and economic analysis, analysis and summarization of the results of economic comparison, SWOT analysis, as well as economic-mathematical modeling and econometric analysis methods were used in the work of the article. Literature and articles of foreign and national economists were analyzed as the methodological basis of the article.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

At the current stage of the development of the market economy, the formation of an effective economic strategy for the development and operation of enterprises becomes a priority for many sectors of Uzbekistan. For this, it is important not only to methodically create tools for quantitative and qualitative evaluation of the proposed economic strategy, but also to develop an appropriate mechanism for its implementation. In particular, comparison deserves attention as one of the main tools. Therefore, it is necessary to determine the main task of the research.

The main features of benchmarking in the management of local marketing activities are the analysis of obstacles in the use of industrial enterprises, as well as the practical development of recommendations for their implementation.

The theoretical aspects of the comparison in practice show that classical marketing includes certain components: product, price, location, promotion, but it does not understand the relationship of the interaction processes of all entities in the market system. It did not take long for other areas of marketing activity (marketing interaction, strategic direction of marketing) to appear and be put into practice, one of the most effective and popular, in the early 70s emergent benchmarking. (English benchmark - bench, level, height and character). The application of benchmarking consists of four consecutive steps:

1. Understanding the details of your business processes;
2. Analysis of business processes of other companies;
3. Analyze and compare the results of the companies with the results of their processes and make the necessary adjustments to reduce the gap.

Currently, there are many definitions of comparison and they require analysis. The most common of them is the definition of the concept that belongs to Robert Kemp: "Benchmarking is the development of activities in which a company applies reporting practices relevant to this industry and improves its results." In addition, Michael Spendolini's definition: "Benchmarking is a 'best practice' to be recognized as an ongoing systematic process of evaluating an organization's products, services and production processes."

We propose to consider benchmarking as a special tool for studying the experience of the best market participants, which has a positive effect on efficiency, and applying the obtained results for marketing activities, quality analysis and corrective conditions of the enterprise.

1 Уваров В. В. Бенчмаркинг как современный метод управления бизнесом // Менеджмент в России и за рубежом. – 2005 – №4. – С. 35–37.

2 Багиев Г.Л. Маркетинг: Учебник / Г.Л. Багиев В.М. Тарасевич Х. Анн; Под общ. ред. Г.Л. Багиева. 2-е изд., перераб. и доп. - М.: Экономика, 2003.-718 с.

The objectives of comparing enterprises are the following rules: The principles of implementation of the concept of benchmarking are the management of enterprises presented in their current form. Adherence to the principles of benchmarking is the basis for creating an effective and efficient economic strategy of the enterprise and ensures a certain stage of implementation. In addition, the main principles of benchmarking are³:

1. Use of information - a special method of management in order to carry out and apply comparisons requires access to information about the work of other organizations, some aspects of their activities. It is especially difficult to find information on specific areas of work that should include innovative developments, customer base;
2. Transparency of information - this principle is very similar to the principle of content, but its observance is directly related to the provision of intellectual property rights, which is the business of the business entity. Transparency of data collection through surveys, meetings, and similar paid engagement of business experts. In this case, the entire process of data collection should be completely transparent.
3. The reliability of information is the essence of the principle of comparison, its effectiveness is the main guarantee of the rational use of benchmarking as a method of increasing the accuracy of real data, and the quality of management in the enterprise is based only on reliable data.
4. Existence of a sample - one of the main principles of benchmarking management - is the existence of a similar enterprise, which is also used to improve economic activity in relation to the main business entity that has to perform very similar work. If its scope is significant, it is very difficult to find such an organization and there are many similar enterprises and it is somewhat difficult to choose which enterprise to compare.
5. Systematization - the use of a comprehensive approach to the application of the essence of the benchmarking principle as a management method, that is, the identification of weaknesses, their identification and the development of measures to eliminate them. The principle of structuring is implemented through four main components:
 - systematic analysis of enterprise activity, identification of problems and shortcomings and prevention of their development;
 - to study the market in which the company operates, to identify the leaders in this field and the most developed business entities;
 - search for an analogue of the set of criteria developed by the company to choose the best work model;
 - search and systematization of information about the enterprise - analogue, methods that may be useful for the separation entity, a detailed description of their implementation mechanisms. In fact, the principle of systematic comparison should be applied at all stages, because each of them should make informed decisions in order to better understand the general situation and make it more effective by grouping and systematizing the results obtained.
6. Validity of the results - the essence of this principle is to determine those quantitative and qualitative indicators, the direction of which will increase the effectiveness of debt and management that may arise as a result of introducing new changes. This approach makes it possible to assess the feasibility of using comparison, the effectiveness of using the experience of other entities, and the achievement of this goal in general.
7. Availability and quality - the essence of this principle is the need to ensure that the comparison corresponds to the level of quality. The use of such an approach is important in the development of specific measures related to the in-depth economic analysis of individual economic systems. Among them, it is appropriate to include other subjects of management, some branches and branches of the national sphere. Economic finance and its analysis are also important components of the effective use of benchmarking. It is for this reason that the employees of the enterprise may not be able to conduct such research if the employees do not have the appropriate qualifications. Sometimes it is advisable to engage external consultants and clients to conduct appropriate research and develop recommendations in this case. There are a number of advantages to using financial advisors, including experience and speed of getting the information you need.

³ Shabaga T. M. (2015) Special features of storing benchmarking programs at foreign and foreign enterprises. Business Navigator. No. 1. pp. 119-121. - available at: http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/bnav_2015_1_23

8. Objectivity and objectivity - this principle should be considered in two ways. First, objectivity is required by the research process itself, the analysis of reliable data, the correct assessment of competitors should be based on this. On the other hand, impartiality also consists in correctly defining the work of its departments. It is also important to minimize subjective attitudes, correctly assess the work of individual employees, their work efficiency. The process of benchmarking as a special method of improving the efficiency of enterprise management is complex and multi-stage.

Accordingly, with this in mind, we determine what are the common advantages and disadvantages of using comparisons by different companies.

Figure 1: Principles of Benchmarking⁴

To simply define the benchmarking process as a set the following requirements can be set:

- decide what to compare with;
- identification of divisions for comparative analysis;
- development of indicators that allow comparison;
- comparison to identify branches within the enterprise and external enterprises;
- collecting and analyzing benchmarking data;
- to determine the difference between the levels of subsystems of the selected enterprise and the level of the best similar subsystems;
- development of action plans, goals and measurement (evaluation) procedures;
- justification of the need for the comparison process.

Today, interest is constantly growing and there is a great need to study the experience of successful benchmarking studies. As soon as an organization realizes through benchmarking that it is lagging behind benchmarks, it is particularly interested in finding best practices that can help address the causes of this lagging. Obtaining and analyzing such information usually occurs in the process of detailed study of the work of certain organizations.

The benchmarking process typically consists of several steps, from planning to implementation of best practices in your organization. There is no single scheme for conducting the benchmarking process, each organization determines its own sequence of work.

CONCLUSION

Focus on studying practices and business processes rather than formalized quantitative indicators of enterprises. Benchmarking also includes a comparative analysis of performance results to some extent, which allowed it to be considered as a comparison of its performance with the best in the industry or the world. At the same time, within the framework of benchmarking, private, scattered indicators describing individual business processes are analyzed. This is the preparatory stage of comparison or comparative comparison, and the main role is played by the process.

This, in turn, determines the existence of a large number of principles, the observance of which affects the correct use of the mechanism of such a method and the quality of the obtained results.

Summarizing all of the above, we can conclude that today benchmarking is an integral element of company management. It is of particular importance in quality management, which allows to constantly monitor the quality level, to observe the latest trends in product production and service provision. In addition, this tool gives the companies that use it the opportunity to learn directly, to review new products, best practices of other companies, as it facilitates cooperation between the initiating company and the benchmarking partner company, provides.

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Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Xondamir Ismoilov

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